

Research behaviour

Martin Jukes, 11 May, 2012

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RAL Space

Harwell International Space Innovation Centre

What scientists do –

Types of hypothesis

Category	Type of hypothesis
Tools and services	Can algorithm X/package Y improve service Z?
Observations	Can technique X improve accuracy of measurement Y?
Modelling	Can algorithm X make reduce known inaccuracies in model Y?
Science	Does El Nino get stronger in a warmer climate? Does atmospheric pollution change cloud reflectivity?

Challenges

National Centre for Atmospheric Science challenges (from their strategy document):

- Challenge 1: Identify and model the processes that govern climate variability and change on regional and local space scales, and time-scales from months to decades; quantify and reduce the uncertainty in predictions on these scales;
- Challenge 2: Identify and model the processes that govern climate on multi-decadal to centennial time-scales; quantify and reduce the uncertainty in predictions for the next century;
- Challenge 3: Improve the prediction of human exposure to air pollution and the attribution of contributing sources;
- Challenge 4: Improve the capability for predicting high impact weather.

Project types

Model development:

frame a science question (e.g. how do peat bog methane emissions vary with global mean temperature?);

software development to implement representation new processes in a model (e.g. release of methane from peat bogs or influence of black carbon on cloud droplet condensation);

gather observations (from archive or colleagues) to evaluate model performance;

design a series of model experiments;

Project types

Observational campaign:

frame science question (e.g. what happens to car exhausts in an urban environment?);

design or configure an instrument to measure a range of chemical radicals throughout a representative period;

configure a model to assist with interpretation of results (e.g. a transport model which describes advection of pollutants around the city);

gather observations;

Data analysis:

frame science question (e.g. could the Amazon basin dry out in the next 100 years?);

obtain relevant model and observation results from archives;

review current understanding of the relevant physical processes (e.g. circulations driven by sea surface temperature anomalies; variation of transpiration rates with temperature, insolation and CO₂ concentrations);

evaluate ability of model to simulate relevant processes and observed variability; where observed record is short, estimate climate variability from model runs and indirect observations;

interpret model projections;

CMIP5 and AR5: a brief organisational overview

Experiment design
coordinated by Karl Taylor at
PCMDI on behalf of WCRP

Data arriving now –
1100TB in the archive
(c.f. 925TB on Feb 17th –
growing at ~2.5TB/day)

A globally distributed archive,
a federation of data centres
and modelling centres will
host the archive

A rich set of CMIP5 experiments, drawn from several predecessor MIPs, focuses on model evaluation, projections, and understanding

Red subset matches the entire CMIP3 experimental suite

Green subset is for coupled carbon-cycle climate models only

Adapted from Taylor et al., BAMS, 2011

"Long-term" experiments: planned contributions

* *Core simulations* (# available as of 5 Feb 2012)

Experiment(s)	# of models
* Control & historical	35 (23)
* AMIP	26 (13)
* RCP4.5 & 8.5	29 (21)
RCP2.6	18 (18)
RCP6	14 (14)
RCP's to year 2300	10 (?)
* 1% CO2 increase	28 (18)
* Fixed SST CO2 forcing diagnosis	16 (9)
* Abrupt 4XCO2 diagnostic	22 (17)

Experiment(s)	# of models
Fast adjustment diagnostic	9 (?)
Aerosol forcing	9 (5)
*ESM control, historical & RCP8.5	18 (7)
Carbon cycle feedback isolation	9 (6)
Mid-Holocene & LGM	11 (6,1)
Millenium	7 (4)
CFMIP runs	7-9 (5)
D & A runs	15 (12)

The climate assessment process

**British Atmospheric
Data Centre**

NATIONAL CENTRE FOR ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

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Climate diagnostics benchmarks

Benchmarking data processing workflows

- Should we move the calculation to a machine with fast archive access, or move the data to a machine with fast processing?
- What is the data reduction achieved by the processing?
- What is the probability of needing to do the calculation again, or how many times do you expect to do the calculation?
- E.g. calculating daily cyclone distributions → reduce data by a factor 3; monthly mean cyclone distribution → reduce data by a factor 100.

Sea-level pressure DJF

Precipitation DJF

Working with

PCMDI and DKRZ to ensure a functioning archive infrastructure and long term preservation of the data;
GO-ESSP: to provide a comprehensive set of data services;
IPCC TGICA: to establish standards for